

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF PERSONALIZED LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

Yorqin Alijanovich Shukurov

Docent V.B., Al-Azhar Department of
Arabic Language and Literature,
Uzbekistan International Islamic Academy

Abstract: *This article examines the role and significance of personalized learning technologies in enhancing the quality of education in general secondary schools. The necessity of students selecting their own life goals and principles is also discussed.*

Keywords: *school, quality of education, educational technology, personalized technologies, pedagogical technology, pedagogical activity, education, student, teacher.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматривается роль и значение персонализированных технологий обучения в повышении качества образования в общеобразовательных школах. Также обсуждается необходимость выбора студентами собственных жизненных целей и принципов.*

Ключевые слова: *школа, качество образования, образовательные технологии, персонализированные технологии, педагогическая технология, педагогическая деятельность, образование, студент, учитель.*

Annotatsiya: Bu maqolada ta'lim sifatini oshirishda shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim texnologiyalarining o'rni va ahamiyati, shuningdek maktab bitiruvchilarining hayotiy maqsad va tamoyillarni tanlashdagi zarurati yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim sifati, ta'lim texnologiyasi, shaxsga yo'naltirilgan texnologiyalar, pedagogik texnologiya, pedagogik faoliyat, ta'lim, o'quvchi, o'qituvchi.

In today's era of rapidly developing information and communication technologies, there is a growing need to consider the individual capabilities and needs of learners. Education is seen as a key factor in the professional development of an individual. Therefore, education must be personalized, corresponding to the learner's life aspirations, needs, and interests. This implies that instruction should be differentiated, taking into account the level of knowledge acquisition and individual abilities.

Traditional education, which has long dominated educational systems in many developed countries and has been designed for learners with average abilities, is no longer meeting the needs of contemporary learners. Ongoing research and analyses of educational effectiveness and prospects have shown that traditional education is unable to meet the societal demand for the cultivation of free, independent, and comprehensively developed individuals. A more advanced educational system should be able to fully realize the learners' internal potential and develop their abilities.

Throughout history, education systems have always served to meet certain social, economic, cultural, and scientific-technical needs. These needs, firstly, serve as a basis

for setting educational goals; secondly, they stimulate the creation of conditions necessary for achieving educational goals and improving them. Socio-economic factors are the primary basis for the development of an educational system. It is precisely the socio-economic structure of society that, in conjunction with many other factors, makes it possible to create the conditions necessary for shaping and developing an educational system. Scientific and technological progress, the existing cultural and socio-ideological environment stimulate or hinder social and economic changes in society, including the development of the educational system¹.

One of the most important tasks facing the educational system is to help society solve the social, economic, and cultural problems that arise.

It is important for educational institutions to be able to quickly respond to the social demands placed on them, to adapt to new situations, and at the same time, to preserve the accumulated advanced experience. Research shows that educational institutions are somewhat conservative, and most of the teachers working in them adapt very slowly to the ongoing social and economic changes and scientific and technological progress. Innovations are often not positively received. For innovations and advanced experiences to be positively accepted by teachers and students, a certain amount of time is required.

However, in the context of global information exchange, the issue of adopting innovative pedagogical technologies and using them effectively in the educational process should not be met with objections. If in the past, when traditional education prevailed, teaching played a leading role in the educational system, in the current conditions, independent learning is a crucial aspect of the system. Therefore, it is now more appropriate to use the principle of “student – textbook – teacher” instead of the traditional “teacher – textbook – student” principle. According to this principle, the main task of the teacher is to organize the students' activities aimed at independent learning in accordance with specific educational goals, to teach them to independently acquire knowledge and actively apply the theoretical knowledge they have acquired in practice. Now, the teacher should focus not so much on transmitting ready-made knowledge to students, but rather on teaching them to independently acquire knowledge from various sources, develop independent, critical thinking, prove their personal points of view, and select effective methods that allow them to enrich the previously acquired knowledge with new information.

It is known that at the beginning of the 20th century, the structure of educational activities was such that students were required to be active participants in a process consisting of a set of specific subjects (for example, one hour of mathematics, one hour of physics, one hour of literature, music, etc.) every day. At the end of the lessons, homework was assigned for these very subjects. Students found it difficult to connect the knowledge they acquired in these subjects, and they experienced difficulties in understanding the systemic interconnectedness between subjects.

The renowned Russian pedagogue B.S. Gershunskiy, foreseeing the predominant pedagogical principles in the 21st-century education system, draws attention to the

¹ Abraham Harold Masloou. Motivation and Personality. Year of the edition: 2019, p: 35.

need to redirect the research on improving the effectiveness of the pedagogical process. In doing so, it is advisable to achieve the following:

- To shift from the student's executive, result-oriented activities to organizing creative and inquisitive activities at all stages of the educational process;
- To transition from ensuring the unity of goals, content, methods, tools, and organizational forms of education, upbringing, and development, to individualizing and differentiating the educational and cognitive activities of learners;
- To shift from subordinating all elements of the educational process to a single idea to ensuring the ideological plurality and freedom of learners in choosing life goals and principles;
- To achieve a harmony between technocratic and humanistic trends and the predominant system of principles, enabling the pedagogical and cognitive activities of teachers and learners to be in harmony with natural development.

Therefore, the following trends are evident in the future development of education systems in modern society: ensuring the intellectual and moral development of an individual based on diverse, independent, and purposeful activities in various fields of knowledge. Developed countries such as the United States, Great Britain, France, Germany, Canada, and others have adopted this direction as the primary one in implementing educational reforms. Accordingly, the following three important tasks have been set:

1. Reforming the education system;
2. Recognizing the independence, activity, and critical thinking of learners as the leading principles of education and upbringing;
3. Integrating advanced information technologies and technical means into the educational process.

Until recently, in a situation where the classroom system was widely used to transmit knowledge to learners, it was considered impossible to effectively solve the aforementioned tasks using a traditional approach. However, with the adoption of the Republic of Uzbekistan's Law on Education, the situation has changed dramatically. In the years since the country gained independence, sufficient conditions have been created to address the leading tasks of educational reform, and these tasks have been successfully addressed. So, what were the necessary conditions created in this process? These include:

1. Taking into account the opportunity for each learner to actively participate in the learning process;
2. Exploring the possibilities of establishing cooperation between teachers and learners.

To address the priority tasks set in educational reforms, it is necessary to combine the efforts of all educational institutions operating within the continuous education system, as well as the state and society. Educational institutions are now actively working to strengthen existing knowledge, enrich it, and meet the need for continuous self-improvement through the use of modern information technologies and distance learning.

This urgent pedagogical problem must be solved effectively, consistently, and in a short period of time. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the nature of the relationship between the main elements and organizational components of the education system, to identify the key link in creating a unified chain, that is, to achieve the specific goals of education in new social and economic conditions.

In our opinion, the key link in the unified chain of the education system is the use of advanced pedagogical and information technologies in the teaching process. They cannot be separated from each other. After all, the widespread use of advanced pedagogical technologies leads to a change in educational paradigms. And only new information technologies create the opportunity to effectively use the potential inherent in advanced pedagogical technologies.

Today, modern pedagogical education requires the creation of a stable and effective education system that takes into account not only the socio-economic and demographic situation but also historical and cultural traditions.

It is known that pedagogical activity requires a significant expenditure of intellectual, emotional, physical, and nervous energy. Only through such expenditure of energy can a process of understanding and communication be organized that ensures the social activity of an individual. Systematic organization of educational activities leads to the establishment of a conscious activity process, and in this process, important personal qualities such as general competence, diligence, industriousness, independence, social activity, responsibility, and others are formed². The emergence of a new nature of activity satisfies the need for personality formation, and the satisfaction of this need serves as the initial basis and foundation for the development of individual potential.

State educational standards developed for each subject taught in general education institutions, in accordance with the established directions, imply the necessity of developing certain levels of knowledge, skills, and competencies among students. The psychological characteristics and individual abilities of students do not always allow them to sufficiently master the required levels of knowledge, skills, and abilities. Modern teaching technologies based on advanced ideas play a crucial role in solving this problem.

The renowned Russian pedagogue B.S. Gershunskiy³, identifying the priority characteristics of the 21st century, emphasizes the need to focus on the following when determining ways to improve the effectiveness of the pedagogical process:

1. The predominance of creative and research elements in the activities of learners at all stages of the educational process;
2. The individualization and differentiation of the educational and cognitive activities of learners, rejecting the rigid unification of the goals, content, methods, tools, and organizational forms of education, upbringing, and development;

² Abraham Harold Masloou. *Motivation and Personality*. Year of the edition: 2019, p: 67.

³ Гершунский Б. С. Прогностические методы в педагогике. М., Просвещение. 2011, P.:34-36.

3. Ensuring the diversity of opinions, understanding of social reality, building mutual trust, and the freedom to choose paths of moral development, overcoming the subordination of all components of the educational process to a single idea;

4. Ensuring the natural unity of the educational and cognitive activities of teachers and learners, eliminating the disproportionate system of technocratic and humanistic trends.

From the expressed ideas, it becomes clear that in modern society, the strategic direction of developing the education system is to ensure the intellectual and moral development of an individual through the independent acquisition of knowledge, skills, and competencies in various fields. In developing education in this direction, it has been recognized that the following three main tasks are of paramount importance⁴:

1. Reforming the education system;

2. Recognizing the independence, activity, and critical thinking of learners as the leading principles of education and upbringing;

3. Effective use of advanced information technologies in the educational process.

As a result of using innovative educational technologies, students should develop the ability to independently design educational programs and successfully implement them. After all, a professional's competence consists not only in applying theoretical knowledge in practice but also in being able to choose appropriate methods and effective ways of teaching based on the existing knowledge.

Educational activity, as one of the main types of human social activity, is carried out through the expenditure of intellectual, emotional, and physical energy associated with the perception of material reality and the organization of social relations. As a result of systematic training, conscious processes are coordinated, and important psychological qualities of students, such as general abilities, independence, social activity, responsibility, and other important qualities, are developed. Emerging new needs in students ensure the variability of educational activities, and the satisfaction of these needs is an important factor in revealing individual creative potential.

The use of the modeling method based on pedagogical activity activates the professional orientation of students and helps them to be well-equipped with theoretical and practical knowledge. This method improves the pedagogical speech of students, develops their ability to exert a pedagogical influence, and enhances their skills in deep analysis, observation, and accurate and rational evaluation of existing situations.

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